

Ensuring the Quality of Citizen Science Data Using Spatiotemporal Features

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Abstract

This study applied logistic regression, random forest, and gradient boosting to classify insect observations in Brazil (2008–2025) as Research Grade or Needs ID, excluding the very small Casual class. Feature engineering focused on user engagement, geolocation, temporal, and contextual attributes, evaluating the predictive power of spatiotemporal features independently. Gradient boosting achieved the best performance (Test AUC = 0.8696, accuracy = 72%), performing well on the majority class but lower on the minority class, with consistent overall F1 scores. The top-ranked feature, user research rate, indicates that user activity strongly drives classification, while non-geographical features generally outweighed spatiotemporal attributes. These findings suggest that models incorporating user behavior and contextual data generalize better than those relying solely on spatiotemporal features, and future work should explore other animal types and regions to assess the generalization of these results.

1 Introduction

Citizen science involves public participation in the generation of scientific knowledge. In the current post-digital age, increased technological accessibility and widespread availability of data have expanded the reach of these initiatives, facilitating greater engagement and more substantial contributions [6]. Nevertheless, some inherent challenges remain, such as uneven geographic data distribution, often concentrated in densely populated areas, and a higher risk of misidentification [3], both of which may introduce biases into research outcomes [10].

Insects play a vital role in numerous ecological processes, making them an essential subject of study. In Brazil, increased public engagement with insects [11] and targeted conservation efforts [9] have significantly expanded the spatial and temporal coverage of insect records. Platforms like *iNaturalist*³ facilitate this by providing standardized spatiotemporal metadata and descriptive sighting information, enabling reproducible analyses and effective data curation [5].

On the platform, an observation is recorded as a sighting of an organism accompanied by evidence such as images or audio, alongside georeferenced coordinates and the date of the sighting. Observations can achieve "Research Grade" status when community consensus [1] identifies the organism at the species level or at the most precise taxonomic rank feasible below family. For insect observations in Brazil between 2008 and 2025, approximately 32% achieved this status.

In this study, we aim to classify insect observations as either "Research Grade" or "Needs ID," assessing the performance of each classification through three machine learning methods: logistic regression, random forest, and gradient boosting, with a particular emphasis on spatiotemporal attributes. Specifically, we focus on evaluating how well this type of feature can perform independently of other features, including geographic

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precision, positioning methodology and devices, spatial distribution patterns, and contextual location-based characteristics, and how they influence data quality.

This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we describe the dataset, our feature-engineering choices and model evaluation procedures; Section 3 presents and analyzes the experimental outcomes; and Section 4 discusses the key findings, their implications and limitations, and concludes with directions for future research.

2 Methodology

The dataset used in this study comprises insect sightings recorded in Brazil between 2008 and 2025. A total of 1,543,495 samples were obtained, with 67.3% classified as "Needs ID," 0.4% as "Casual," and 32.3% as "Research Grade," according to *iNaturalist's* guidelines. Only the "Needs ID" and "Research Grade" classes were used in the analysis, since the proportion of "Casual" records is very small and many submissions on the platform remain in the "Needs ID" category.

To extract meaningful insights from the dataset, feature engineering was performed, focusing on factors known to directly influence the quality of observations [12]. User attributes, location data, media type, documentation completeness, temporal characteristics, initial identification, and contextual variables were selected as representative features contributing to observation quality.

Three distinct machine learning models were employed for testing classification performance: logistic regression, random forest, and gradient boosting, generally associated with superior predictive capability. All models were trained using default configurations from scikit-learn, employing 10-fold stratified cross-validation preserving class proportions across fold.

Logistic regression serves as a strong, interpretable linear baseline and produces well calibrated probabilities [8]. Random forest is widely used as a robust ensemble approach on tabular data, while gradient boosted trees remain among the strongest performers on such tasks [7] [4].

Model performance was evaluated using the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC-ROC) metric [2], recommended for binary classification tasks due to its capacity to measure a model's discriminative ability. AUC-ROC values range from 0 to 1, with values closer to 1 indicating better performance. This metric is computed as follows:

$$\text{AUC} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (FPR_{i+1} - FPR_i) \cdot \frac{TPR_{i+1} + TPR_i}{2}$$

3 Results

Table 1 shows the performance of the models in cross-validation and in the test set, where the results in bold indicate the best performance.

Table 1. Comparison of models with different feature sets

	Random Forest	Gradient Boosting	Logistic Regression
Model with Full Feature Set			
CV AUC	0.8638	0.8694	0.8546
Test AUC	0.8641	0.8696	0.8516
Model with Spatiotemporal Features			
CV AUC	0.6538	0.6567	0.5873
Test AUC	0.6554	0.6575	0.5866

The best performance was achieved by Gradient Boosting in both scenarios, reaching 0.8696 on the test set. The ROC curves exhibited very similar shapes across methods. When models were trained with the full feature set, all curves lay clearly above the diagonal and were tightly clustered. By contrast, in the scenario with only spatiotemporal features, the curves shifted downward and closer to the diagonal for all methods, reflecting uniformly lower discrimination.

Table 2 provides a more detailed view of the best model’s performance on the test set. With an accuracy of 72% on the test set, the model performs well on the majority class (Needs ID) but struggles with the minority class (Research). The harmonic mean of the F1 scores indicates that, despite this imbalance, the model maintained a consistent overall performance.

Table 2. Detailed performance of Gradient Boosting with Full Feature Set

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
0 (Needs ID)	0.73	0.93	0.82	313,644
1 (Research)	0.66	0.27	0.39	149,405
Overall Accuracy			0.72	463,049

Table 3 shows the 10 most important variables, where the non-geographical variable has a substantially higher importance compared to the others.

Table 3. Top 10 most important variables of Gradient Boosting with Full Feature Set

Variable	Importance
user research rate	0.718196
taxon geoprivacy encoded	0.085623
lat lon interaction	0.048857
user total obs	0.036355
user experience days	0.028933
creation delay	0.019937
latitude percentile	0.017829
lat squared	0.009301
longitude percentile	0.004137
lon squared	0.003588

The cumulative share for the top 3 features is 85.27%, rising to 91.80% for the top 5. Among the top ten, six pertain to geographic data and four capture user activity.

4 Discussion

All the models selected for the study performed similarly to each other. However, the model that relied solely on spatiotemporal features showed lower generalization. In contrast, the model incorporating the other features demonstrated good generalization on the data, reinforcing that the importance assigned to the features is consistent within the analyzed context.

The variable user research rate stands out as the top-ranked feature. This indicates that the frequency with which a user engages in research-related observations strongly influences the model’s classification, reflecting that more active and involved users are more likely to submit high-quality sightings. Its dominant importance suggests that user behavior and engagement carry far more predictive power than individual geographic or temporal characteristics when determining whether an observation is classified as Research Grade.

However, the seasonality of observations and the exact accuracy of the species' location do not strongly influence whether a sighting is considered Research Grade, meaning these factors are not given as much weight in the model's decisions.

Future work may also consider other types of animals, as well as other regions with different ecological and socio-economic conditions, verifying whether similar biases in feature importance and observation quality exist in different contexts, and better understanding how generalizable the findings from this study are across diverse datasets and environments.

Furthermore, the core methodology of this study could be extended to entirely different fields of citizen science. For instance, in space research, volunteers contribute to tasks such as classifying celestial objects or analyzing planetary surfaces. In such contexts, our finding that user engagement metrics are paramount for data quality could help develop more effective validation systems, likely proving more critical than the specific coordinates of an observed star or galaxy. This highlights the potential for a universal framework where user reliability is a key feature for ensuring data quality across various scientific domains.

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